

IPPT_TWINN - Reinforcing the scientific excellence and innovation capacity in polymer processing technologies of the Faculty of Polymer Technology

PROJECT: 101079051 – IPPT_TWINN – HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03

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Institution: Faculty of Polymer Technology (FTPO)

WP6 - DISSEMINATION, EXPLOITATION,
OUTREACH, AND COMMUNICATION

D6.3 GUIDELINES FOR PROJECT'S VISUAL IDENTITY

CONTACT DETAILS

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PROJECT DETAILS

Project Number	101079051
Project Acronym	IPPT_TWINN
Project Name	Reinforcing the scientific excellence and innovation capacity in polymer processing technologies of the Faculty of Polymer Technology
Starting date	1 st January 2023
Duration in months	36
Call (part) identifier	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03
Action	Twinning - Institutional networking

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Author	Roman Kerschbaumer, Viktorija Zanoškar, Blaž Nardin, Maja Mešl
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VERSION MANAGEMENT

Revision history and quality check			
Version	Name	Date	Comment
V0.1	Viktorija Zanoškar, Maja Mešl	29 th May 2023	First draft
V1	Roman Kerschbaumer, Viktorija Zanoškar, Blaž Nardin, Maja Mešl	14 th June 2023	Confirmed at 1 st project progress meeting

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SYMBOL | BASIC IDEA

POLYMERS + BRAINS + MOVE FORWARD + COOPERATING & CONNECTING

SYMBOL | BASIC IDEA

POLYMERS | ABSTRACT SHAPES

SYMBOL | BASIC IDEA

BRAINS | IMAGINARY OUTER FORM

SYMBOL | BASIC IDEA

MOVE FORWARD | ABSTRACT-HIDDEN DIRECTIONAL SIGN

SYMBOL | BASIC IDEA

COOPERATING & CONNECTING | CONNECTED ELEMENTS IN PICTOGRAM

SYMBOL

SYMBOL REPRESENTS

POLYMERS + BRAINS + MOVE FORWARD + COOPERATING & CONNECTING

SYMBOL + TYPOGRAPHIC PART = LOGOTYPE

LOGOTYPE | PRIMARY

COLOR VARIANT – HORIZONTAL

USAGE: ON BRIGHT BACKGROUNDS

LOGOTYPE | PRIMARY

COLOR NEGATIVE VARIANT – HORIZONTAL

USAGE: ON CORPO GRAYISH DARK BLUE & DARK BACKGROUNDS

LOGOTYPE | PRIMARY

COLOR NEGATIVE VARIANT 2 – HORIZONTAL

USAGE: ON CORPO YOUTHFUL GREEN BACKGROUNDS

LOGOTYPE | PRIMARY

NEGATIVE VARIANT – HORIZONTAL

USAGE: ON CORPO GRAYISH DARK BLUE & DARK BACKGROUNDS

LOGOTYPE | SECONDARY

COLOR VARIANT - VERTICAL

USAGE: ON BRIGHT BACKGROUNDS, ONLY IF THERE IS NOT ENOUGH SPACE FOR THE HORIZONTAL VARIANT

LOGOTYPE | SECONDARY

COLOR NEGATIVE VARIANT - VERTICAL

USAGE: ON CORPO GRAYISH DARK BLUE & DARK BACKGROUNDS, ONLY WHEN THERE IS NO SPACE FOR A HORIZONTAL VARIANT

LOGOTYPE | SECONDARY

COLOR NEGATIVE VARIANT - VERTICAL

USAGE: ON CORPO YOUTHFUL GREEN BACKGROUNDS, ONLY WHEN THERE IS NO SPACE FOR A HORIZONTAL VARIANT

LOGOTYPE | SECONDARY

NEGATIVE VARIANT - VERTICAL

USAGE: ON CORPO GRAYISH DARK BLUE & DARK BACKGROUNDS, ONLY WHEN THERE IS NO SPACE FOR A HORIZONTAL VARIANT

SYMBOL | CONSTRUCTION

3 BY 3 CIRCLE PATTERN ON 2 BY 2 SQUARE GRID , TURNED BY 45°

LOGOTYPE | SAFETY AREA

IT IS RECOMMENDED THAT NO OTHER GRAPHIC ELEMENTS
SHOULD NOT BE CLOSER THAN SPECIFIED

LOGOTYPE | MINIMAL LOGO DIMENSION RECOMMENDATION ...

... IN PRINTED MEDIA

... IN DIGITAL MEDIA

COLORS | PRIMARY

YOUTHFUL
GREEN

PMS 2301 C
RGB 143 173 26
HTML 8FAD1A

SHADES OF YOUTHFUL GREEN

THE MEANING OF COLORS

FRESH | YOUTHFUL | GROWTH | RESTORATION | ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS | NEW BEGINNINGS

COLORS | PRIMARY

PMS 2182 C
RGB 23 74 93
HTML 174A5D

SHADES OF GRAYISH DARK BLUE

THE MEANING OF COLORS

STEADFAST, RESPONSIBLE, CONSCIENTIOUS, CONSERVATIVE, SOPHISTICATED, SOLID, ENDURING

COLORS | SECONDARY

WINTER SKY
BLUE

PMS 4157 C
RGB 100 174 202
HTML 64AECA

FLAME
RED

PMS 7626 C
RGB 199 54 45
HTML C7362D

DEEP
BLACK

100 K
RGB 0 0 0
HTML 000000

ABSOLUTE
WHITE

-
RGB 256 256 256
HTML FFFFFFFF

USAGE

SECONDARY COLORS HELP US TO DESIGN CONTENT
PRIMARY COLORS TAKES THE LEAD - SECONDARY COLORS SHOULD BE USED GENTLY & WISELY

TYPOGRAPHY | PRIMARY

Brandon Grotesque - light

ABCČDEFGHIJKLMNOPRSŠTUVZŽ abcčdefghijklmnoprsštuvzž 1234567890 !"#%&'()*=?*.,;:-

Brandon Grotesque - regular

ABCČDEFGHIJKLMNOPRSŠTUVZŽ abcčdefghijklmnoprsštuvzž 1234567890 !"#%&'()*=?*.,;:-

Brandon Grotesque - medium

ABCČDEFGHIJKLMNOPRSŠTUVZŽ abcčdefghijklmnoprsštuvzž 1234567890 !"#%&'()*=?*.,;:-

Brandon Grotesque - bold

ABCČDEFGHIJKLMNOPRSŠTUVZŽ abcčdefghijklmnoprsštuvzž 1234567890 !"#%&'()*=?*.,;:-

Brandon Grotesque - black

ABCČDEFGHIJKLMNOPRSŠTUVZŽ abcčdefghijklmnoprsštuvzž 1234567890 !"#%&'()*=?*.,;:-

TYPOGRAPHY | PRIMARY

TYPOGRAPHY IS WHAT LANGUAGE LOOK LIKE

THE MEANING OF »BRANDON GROTESQUE« TYPOGRAPHIC FAMILY

VERY CLEAN | BASIC | TRUSTWORTHY | LEGIBLE | READABLE | CORPORATIVE | POWERFUL

TYPOGRAPHY | SECONDARY

Calibri - light

ABCČDEFGHIJKLMNOPRSŠTUVZŽ abcčdefghijklmnoprsštuvzž 1234567890 !"#%&'()=?*.,;:-

Calibri - regular

ABCČDEFGHIJKLMNOPRSŠTUVZŽ abcčdefghijklmnoprsštuvzž 1234567890 !"#%&'()=?*.,;:-

Calibri - BOLD

ABCČDEFGHIJKLMNOPRSŠTUVZŽ abcčdefghijklmnoprsštuvzž 1234567890 !"#%&'()=?*.,;:-

USAGE

DON'T WORRY IF »BRANDON GROTESQUE« IS NOT AVAILABLE. IN THAT CASE USE »CALIBRI«.

»CALIBRI« IS USED IN ALL E-COMMUNICATION SUCH AS E-MAIL, WORD, POWERPOINT ...

COMMUNICATIONS | POSTERS

COMMUNICATIONS | POSTERS

1st IPPT_TWINN WORKSHOP

Additive manufacturing

12th, 13th April 2023 | Rapperswil, Switzerland

IWK | Institute for Materials Technology and Plastics Processing

SUMMARY OF THE WORKSHOP
 This workshop provides an overview of 3D-printing processes for plastics, including the latest trends and potentials for industrial applications. It covers three main processes: Arburg Freeformer (APF), SLS, and FFF. Attendees will engage in hands-on workshops, covering FFF with fibers, APF, and SLS. The workshop will also include a design session for additive manufacturing and a factory tour.

Free of charge | On-site and on-line | More information at www.ippt-twinn.eu

	Day 1 (12.04.2023)	Day 2 (13.04.2023)
morning	Lecture: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overview, trends, and potentials (APF, SLS and FFF) 	Excursion / Factory Tour
afternoon	Workshops in two groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> FFF with fibers APF 	Workshops in two groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> SLS Design for Additive Manufacturing

A detailed Agenda will be provided after registration.

ABOUT THE ORGANIZER
 The IWK, or Institute for Plastic Processing and Material Technologies, is a research institute affiliated with the Eastern Switzerland University of Applied Sciences. With its focus on the most important polymer processing methods, the IWK has become a center of expertise in Switzerland and has a team of around 50 employees. www.ost.ch/iwk

MENTORS OF THE WORKSHOP
 Daniel Omidvarkarjan, MSc. ETH, Head of Additive Manufacturing at IWK

Maximum number of on-site participants: 15

Mandatory registration: bianca.fahrni@ost.ch, until 31st of March 2023

Funded by the European Union

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www.ippt-twinn.eu

COMMUNICATIONS | BANNERS

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Funded by the European Union

FTPO
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IWK
IWK INSTITUTE FOR MATERIALS TECHNOLOGY AND PLASTICS PROCESSING

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COMMUNICATIONS | EMBLEMS FOR THE EVENTS

Funded by
the European Union

PARTNERS
